

USE OF MARKETING COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN PRINTING COMPANIES

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the main traditional and modern marketing communications tools used in the retail industry as ways to build relationships with consumers and manage them. The necessity and relevance of the use of these tools by trading enterprises in current market conditions is substantiated. The features of using marketing communications tools and their impact on the target audience, advantages and disadvantages are highlighted. Examples of the practical use of marketing communications tools by retail chains are given.

Keywords: retail trade, marketing, marketing communications, tools, sales promotion, target audience.

INTRODUCTION

The retail sector has undergone significant changes in recent years. The dynamics of consumption are growing, the market is becoming saturated with interchangeable goods, the market power of buyers is strengthening and their sensitivity to price levels is increasing, online trading is developing rapidly, which is due to the current situation in the country and the growing demands of buyers for a comfortable consumer experience. Trade competition is increasing. To maintain the competitiveness and profitability of a business, in addition to optimizing the business processes of organizations, ensuring their flexibility and adaptability to market changes, it is necessary to establish long-term mutually beneficial relationships with consumers, which becomes possible through the use of marketing communications tools.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Marketing communications are a system of tools used to convey information about a company, a specific product or service to the target audience [1]. Organizations use marketing communications tools to increase brand awareness, create a positive company image, consumer loyalty and brand commitment, disseminate information about a new product and, ultimately, to stimulate sales. The relevance of using a marketing communications system in modern companies is due to their focus not only on attracting new customers, but also on maintaining loyalty and retaining existing ones, as well as on developing long-term relationships with them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to constant changes in market conditions and consumer preferences, improvements in technology and information support, and increased competition, there is a continuous improvement of elements of marketing communications, and the emergence of new modern tools to replace those that have lost their effectiveness [2]. Despite the current lack of a unified idea of the composition of the marketing communications complex, we will highlight its main tools used in the retail industry:

- advertising;
- sales promotion;
- public relations (PR);
- internal marketing;
- integrated marketing communications at points of sale;
- Internet Marketing.

The choice of tools and channels of marketing communications in the field of trade should be made by a retail trade enterprise or network based on their format, stage of the life cycle, geography of presence, portrait of the target audience, capabilities and other factors.

Advertising is a form of communication that is informative or incentive in nature and is aimed at promoting goods, services, certain ideas, etc. Despite the fact that advertising is one of the means of traditional marketing, as the informatization of society develops, advertising channels and means are constantly being improved. Retail trade networks widely use outdoor advertising (billboards and banners, stands and signs at bus stops and in residential buildings), transport (on-board and in-cabin), television and print advertising (flyers, brochures and product catalogs, advertising in print media), less often souvenir and radio advertising is used.

Sales promotion includes a set of activities, usually carried out in the short term, aimed at increasing sales or accelerating the sale of goods. The main activities and sales promotion tools used in retail trade include loyalty programs (discount and bonus), discounts and promotions, competitions and sweepstakes, events for the presentation of new products, provision of free product samples, etc. It should be noted that the use of many of the presented methods is quite labor-intensive and involves significant costs, but with proper organization it can contribute to a significant increase in sales. Examples of effective sales promotion activities include the large-scale “Lenta Birthday” campaign, carried out by the Lenta hypermarket chain and including several sales promotion tools: reduced prices on goods, sweepstakes, gifts, refunds for purchases in the form of bonuses, as well as

a promotion “Wheel of Fortune”, which is an example of the effective use of gamification in marketing.

Public relations (PR) can be represented as a set of measures carried out consistently and aimed at the long term to create and maintain a positive image of an enterprise or brand in the minds of consumers, establishing mutual understanding and trust between the organization and the target audience [3].

The digitalization of public life and the development of online commerce require retail trade organizations to use modern marketing communications tools, which are Internet marketing tools. Unlike traditional ones, aimed at the target audience as a whole or its individual large segments (age, geographic, etc.), Internet marketing tools allow, while reaching a wide audience, to personalize interactions with consumers. Internet marketing tools used by retail chains include official websites and online stores, mobile applications, search engine promotion and optimization (SEO), contextual and display advertising, email marketing, and social media promotion (SMM).

CONCLUSION

The use of marketing communications tools by retail chains with a wide geographical presence is complicated by the need to take into account the characteristics, habits and needs of the local target audience. Each of the listed tools has its own application and impact on consumers, advantages and disadvantages, which should be taken into account by companies when developing a marketing strategy. In connection with the development of Internet communications and e-commerce, presence on the Internet is becoming a prerequisite for maintaining business efficiency and ensuring brand recognition.

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